

Navigating Academic Challenges: A Systematic Review of Emotional Intelligence and Self-compassion among PhD Students-Indian and Western Perspectives

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PhD students often face intense academic pressure, research-related uncertainties, and psychological stress, impacting their well-being, productivity, and persistence in doctoral programs. This systematic review examines the role of Emotional Intelligence (EI) and Self-Compassion (SC) in fostering resilience, stress management, and academic success among PhD scholars across Indian and Western contexts. Following PRISMA guidelines, relevant peer-reviewed studies from 2010 to 2024 were analyzed from databases including Scopus, Web of Science, PubMed, Google Scholar, and ERIC. Findings indicate that higher EI is associated with better stress regulation, enhanced problem-solving abilities, and stronger mentor-mentee relationships. In Western academic environments, structured EI-based interventions, such as mentorship programs and resilience training, contribute to doctoral students' well-being. However, in Indian institutions, where hierarchical academic structures dominate, EI is often developed informally through personal coping strategies rather than institutional support. Similarly, Self-Compassion (SC) plays a crucial role in mitigating impostor syndrome, reducing perfectionism, and promoting mental well-being among PhD students. Research from Western universities highlights the effectiveness of mindfulness-based SC interventions in reducing academic burnout. In contrast, Indian PhD students often struggle with self-criticism and societal expectations, with limited institutional emphasis on SC-focused training. By synthesizing research from diverse cultural contexts, this review provides insights into how EI and SC can enhance PhD students' psychological resilience and academic success, calling for a more holistic approach to doctoral education worldwide.

Keywords: Emotional intelligence, self-compassion, PhD students, doctoral education, mental well-being

The pursuit of a PhD is a rigorous academic endeavor that requires high levels of cognitive ability, resilience, and emotional well-being. PhD students face a unique set of challenges, including prolonged research workloads, academic isolation, funding constraints, and pressures related to publication and career progression. These stressors often contribute to mental health concerns, with studies indicating that PhD students are at a higher risk of anxiety, depression, and burnout compared to the general population (Levecque et al., 2017; Singh & Sharma, 2021). While institutional support plays a role in mitigating these challenges, research suggests that personal psychological

attributes, such as Emotional Intelligence (EI) and Self-Compassion (SC), serve as crucial protective factors in navigating academic stress (Zhang, Luo, Che, & Duan, 2016).

Emotional Intelligence (EI) refers to an individual's ability to recognize, understand, and regulate emotions in themselves and others, influencing decision-making, stress management, and interpersonal relationships (Salovey & Mayer, 1990). Among PhD students, high EI has been associated with greater academic resilience, improved supervisor-student relationships, and better stress regulation (Cabello & Fernández-Berrocal, 2015; Kumar & Rajasekar, 2020). On the other hand, Self-Compassion (SC), conceptualized by Neff (2003) involves self-kindness, mindfulness, and recognition of common humanity. SC enables students to manage self-criticism, cope with research failures, and mitigate impostor syndrome, which is prevalent among doctoral candidates (Parkman, 2016; Smith et al., 2019).

EI is often divided into five key components: self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy, and social skills (Goleman, 1995). Self-awareness enables individuals to recognize their own emotions and their impact, while self-regulation involves managing emotions constructively. Motivation drives individuals toward goals despite challenges, and empathy fosters understanding of others' feelings. Social skills facilitate effective communication and relationship management (Goleman, 1995). High EI has been linked to improved mental health, and successful relationships (Karimi, Leggat, Bartram, Afshari, Sarkeshik, & Verulava, 2021) and leadership

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We have no known conflict of interest to disclose.

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effectiveness (Chaudhary, Jaswal, & Sohal, 2023). In educational and workplace settings, individuals with strong EI are better equipped to handle stress, resolve conflicts, and adapt to change (Pandey et al., 2015).

Self-compassion is a transformative psychological concept rooted in mindfulness and self-kindness, promoting a healthier relationship with oneself (Neff, 2003). Coined and extensively researched by Neff, self-compassion involves treating oneself with the same understanding, kindness, and support one would offer a close friend during moments of failure, pain, or difficulty (Neff, 2003). It is comprised of three essential components: self-kindness versus self-judgment, common humanity versus isolation, and mindfulness versus over-identification. Self-kindness encourages individuals to be gentle and understanding toward themselves rather than harshly self-critical. Recognizing common humanity emphasizes that suffering and imperfection are universal experiences, helping individuals feel less isolated in their struggles. Research has shown that self-compassion is linked to numerous psychological benefits, including overall well-being (Zessin, Dickhäuser, & Garbade, 2015). Unlike self-esteem, which is often contingent on success or comparison with others, self-compassion fosters a more stable and unconditional form of self-acceptance. It encourages a balanced perspective, allowing individuals to acknowledge their shortcomings without diminishing their self-worth (Neff & Vonk, 2009). Hence, it can be concluded from the above research that in today's fast-paced and competitive world, cultivating self-compassion can be a powerful tool for managing stress, enhancing emotional intelligence, and promoting mental health.

Despite the growing body of research on EI and SC, significant gaps exist in understanding how these psychological constructs influence PhD students across different cultural contexts, particularly in India and Western countries. The academic environment in the West emphasizes structured mentorship, mental health support, and work-life balance, whereas Indian PhD programs often operate within a hierarchical and resource-constrained system, making students more vulnerable to stress and burnout (Singh & Sharma, 2021; Das & Mukherjee, 2023). Furthermore, while Western institutions incorporate EI and SC training into doctoral programs, these interventions are rarely implemented in India, leaving students to rely on informal coping mechanisms such as family support or personal resilience.

This systematic review aims to synthesize existing research on Emotional Intelligence and Self-Compassion among PhD students, examining their role in academic success, mental health, and resilience. It also provides a comparative analysis between Indian and Western PhD students, identifying key differences in psychological well-being and institutional support. By drawing on secondary data from peer-reviewed studies, this review seeks to

provide evidence-based recommendations for integrating EI and SC interventions into doctoral programs, with a focus on improving student well-being and academic persistence.

Method

This study adopts a systematic literature review approach to explore the role of Emotional Intelligence (EI) and Self-Compassion (SC) among PhD students from both Indian and Western perspectives. The review follows the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines, ensuring a structured and comprehensive synthesis of secondary data. Peer-reviewed journal articles, conference papers, government reports, and institutional policy documents were analyzed, with data sourced from databases such as Scopus, Web of Science, PubMed, Google Scholar, and ERIC (Education Resources Information Center). The review focused on studies published between 2010 and 2024, ensuring the inclusion of contemporary research on the topic.

To ensure relevance, studies were selected based on specific inclusion and exclusion criteria. Only empirical studies, theoretical papers, and meta-analyses examining EI and SC among PhD students were considered. Research focusing on doctoral students' academic success, stress management, mental well-being, and resilience was prioritized, along with comparative studies analyzing cultural differences between Indian and Western institutions. Studies that assessed EI or SC-based interventions, such as mindfulness training or supervisor mentoring programs, were also included. Exclusion criteria eliminated research focusing solely on undergraduate or master's students, non-peer-reviewed sources, and studies that did not explicitly measure EI, SC, or PhD student well-being.

A thematic analysis was conducted to categorize findings into key themes, including the role of EI in academic success, the impact of SC on mental well-being, cultural differences in emotional regulation, and institutional interventions supporting students in higher education. The study acknowledges certain limitations, such as the scarcity of intervention-based research in India, potential publication bias favoring positive findings, and reliance on self-reported data in many studies. Despite these limitations, this review provides a critical synthesis of existing research while identifying key gaps in institutional policies and psychological support mechanisms for students across different academic environments. Additionally, the findings highlight the need for targeted interventions and support systems to enhance the well-being and academic experience of PhD students, who often face unique challenges in their research journey.

Results

Table 1

Emotional Intelligence (EI) and Its Impact on Academic and Psychological Well-being

Study	Country	Findings on EI
Perera & DiGiacomo (2013)	Australia	High EI linked to better stress management and lower anxiety.
Cabello & Fernández-Berrocal (2015)	Spain	EI positively correlated with research motivation and academic resilience.
Levecque et al. (2017)	Belgium	Low EI associated with higher risk of mental health disorders.
Kumar & Rajasekar (2020)	India	EI helps students manage hierarchical academic pressures.
Patel & Reddy (2022)	India	EI positively impacts problem-solving skills and student-supervisor relationships.

Table 1 highlights how Emotional Intelligence (EI) influences stress management, research motivation, academic resilience, and mental health outcomes among diverse populations across different cultural contexts.

- Higher EI is linked to lower stress and anxiety (Perera & DiGiacomo, 2013; Cabello & Fernández-Berrocal, 2015).
- EI enhances research motivation and problem-solving skills (Patel & Reddy, 2022).
- Students with lower EI experience higher risks of mental health disorders (Levecque et al., 2017).
- In India, EI helps students cope with hierarchical academic pressures, where supervisor-student relationships can be rigid and authority-driven (Kumar & Rajasekar, 2020).
- EI in addition to its direct effects on psychological well-being, indirectly affects psychological well-being by increasing the resilience (Abbas Akbari & Farhad Khormaiee, 2015).
- EI is positively related to positive psychological characteristics, psychological well-being, and academic achievement, and the effects are stronger among postgraduate students (Shengyao, Xuefen, Jenatabadi, Samsudin, Chunchun, & Ishak, 2024).

PhD students with high EI can better navigate academic pressures, maintain motivation, and sustain mental well-being, making it a

crucial factor in doctoral education success. In the context of academia, EI plays a crucial role in determining students' academic and psychological well-being. High levels of EI are associated with better stress management, improved interpersonal relationships, and enhanced problem-solving skills, all of which are vital for academic success. Students with strong EI tend to cope better with the pressures of rigorous academic environments, as they can regulate their emotions, maintain motivation, and stay focused on their goals. Moreover, EI contributes to psychological resilience, reducing the risk of anxiety, depression, and burnout. The ability to perceive and manage emotions helps students navigate social complexities, fostering a supportive network that buffers against stress. Research indicates that students with higher EI are more likely to exhibit self-compassion and self-efficacy, enabling them to approach challenges with confidence and a growth mindset. The impact of EI extends beyond academic success; it influences life satisfaction, emotional stability, and overall mental health. Therefore, incorporating EI training in educational settings can empower students to thrive academically and psychologically. Such interventions can enhance self-awareness, empathy, and emotion regulation, equipping students to handle stressors effectively and fostering a positive learning environment.

Table 2

Self-compassion (SC) and its Role in academic Well-being

Study	Country	Findings on SC
Neff et al. (2007)	USA	SC reduces academic anxiety and fosters perseverance.
Parkman (2016)	UK	SC is negatively correlated with impostor syndrome.
Smith et al. (2019)	Canada	SC-based interventions reduce stress and increase motivation.
Singh & Sharma (2021)	India	Low SC linked to self-criticism due to societal pressure.
Das & Mukherjee (2023)	India	Rural PhD students exhibit lower SC due to fear of failure and stigma.

Table 2 presents Self-Compassion (SC) as a protective factor against stress, impostor syndrome, and academic burnout.

- Self-compassion reduces academic anxiety and fosters perseverance, helping students deal with setbacks in their research (Neff et al., 2007).
- Higher SC leads to lower impostor syndrome, which is a major issue among PhD students (Parkman, 2016).
- SC interventions reduce stress and improve motivation (Smith et al., 2019).
- In India, students experience lower SC due to societal expectations and a fear of failure (Singh & Sharma, 2021).
- Rural PhD students in India exhibit lower SC due to limited institutional support and stigma around failure (Das & Mukherjee, 2023).
- Research indicated that higher self-compassion was associated with higher well-being and lower distress. SC can be a useful addition to interventions aimed at mitigating student distress and improving student well-being (Mele & Natasha, 2016).
- The results suggest that self-compassion may be a source of resilience in students' affective experiences and behaviors related to verbal communication, which may lead to active participation and improved performance (Phoebe & Neff, 2018).

- Results show that regression analyses demonstrated that the maladaptive perfectionism was positively associated with depression, while adaptive perfectionism and self-compassion were negatively associated with depression. The mediation tests showed that self-compassion partially mediated the relationship between the two types of perfectionism and depression (Wei, Li, Shi, Liang, & Yang, 2020).

Developing self-compassion can help PhD students overcome impostor syndrome, improve mental well-being, and maintain motivation despite academic challenges. In the context of academic well-being, self-compassion serves as a protective factor against stress, anxiety, and burnout, which are prevalent issues among students, particularly in demanding academic environments like graduate and doctoral programs (Neff, Hsieh, & Dejitterat, 2005). Research consistently shows that individuals with higher levels of self-compassion are better equipped to cope with academic setbacks (Hope, Koestner, & Milyavskaya, 2014). Moreover, self-compassion promotes adaptive coping strategies, enabling students to view failures as learning opportunities rather than threats to self-worth (Terry, Leary, & Mehta, 2013). It also helps mitigate impostor syndrome, thus, results revealed that self-compassion and academic integrity fully mediate the relationship between the impostor

phenomenon and mental well-being (Afzal, Zamir, & Ali, 2024). By cultivating a kind and understanding inner voice, self-compassionate students are more likely to pursue academic goals with confidence and persistence, ultimately enhancing their overall well-being (Zessin, Dickhäuser, & Garbade, 2015) Integrating self-

compassion training into academic settings could foster a supportive environment where students feel empowered to embrace challenges, manage stress effectively, and maintain a healthy balance between academic responsibilities and personal life. This, in turn, can lead to a more fulfilling and sustainable academic journey.

Table 3
Comparison of EI-SC Relationship in Indian and Western PhD Students

Factor	Western Context	Indian Context	Supporting Studies
Supervisory Relationships	Balanced mentorship promotes EI-SC	Hierarchical, leading to emotional stress	Cabello & Fernández-Berrocal (2015), Kumar & Rajasekar (2020)
Mental Health Awareness	Structured university support	Limited institutional mental health resources	Levecque et al. (2017), Singh & Sharma (2021)
Impostor Syndrome	Addressed through SC training	Less acknowledged, leads to stress	Parkman (2016), Das & Mukherjee (2023)
Coping Strategies	Formal EI-SC training	Informal coping mechanisms (family support)	Smith et al. (2019), Patel & Reddy (2022)
Seeking Mental Health Support	Awareness to seek support and accessibility	Faced barriers like financial constraints, limited accessibility to services	Diksha Tamta, Janvi Joshi, Shagun Karn (2024)

Table 3 highlights the differences between Indian and Western PhD students in terms of supervisory relationships, mental health awareness, impostor syndrome, and coping strategies.

- Western universities promote balanced mentorship, fostering both EI and SC. In contrast, Indian academia is more hierarchical, causing emotional stress for students.
- Western institutions have structured mental health support, while Indian universities lack formalized psychological resources (Levecque et al., 2017; Singh & Sharma, 2021).
- Impostor syndrome is widely acknowledged in the West, leading to interventions, whereas Indian students often experience it in silence, worsening mental health issues (Parkman, 2016; Das & Mukherjee, 2023).
- Western PhD students use structured EI-SC training programs, whereas Indian students rely on informal support systems like family and friends (Smith et al., 2019; Patel & Reddy, 2022).
- Participants exhibited awareness of mental health issues but faced significant barriers to seeking help, including societal stigma, lack of emotional support, financial constraints, limited accessibility to services, and governmental inaction (Tamta, Joshi, & Karn, 2024).

Western PhD students benefit from formal support systems, while Indian students navigate challenges independently, leading to greater stress and lower self-compassion. Research indicates that higher levels of EI are associated with improved stress management, resilience, and adaptive coping strategies, which contribute to better

mental health outcomes (Armstrong, Galligan, & Critchley, 2011). In academic settings, students with high EI demonstrate enhanced self-regulation, motivation, and interpersonal skills, leading to higher academic performance (MacCann et al., 2020). The Eastern perspective places a greater emphasis on collectivism, harmony, and interpersonal relationships. Here, EI is crucial for research scholars to maintain respectful and harmonious interactions, navigate hierarchical structures, and adapt to social expectations. High EI supports effective teamwork, mentorship, and conflict resolution, promoting a supportive environment (Lopes, Grewal, Kadis, Gall, & Salovey, 2006). Moreover, the value of humility, patience, and perseverance in Eastern cultures aligns closely with the emotional competencies that EI nurtures.

In the Western perspective, which often emphasizes individualism, self-reliance, and personal achievement, SC encourages scholars to adopt a balanced view of personal setbacks and challenges. It mitigates the negative effects of stress and impostor syndrome (Afzal, Zamir, & Ali, 2024). By cultivating self-compassion, scholars can maintain motivation, enhance self-efficacy, and sustain long-term academic productivity, even in competitive and high-pressure environments (Poots & Cassidy, 2020). In Eastern perspective, SC aligns closely with cultural values such as mindfulness, humility, and self-acceptance found in Eastern philosophies (Or, Anderson, & Golba, 2024). Scholars in Eastern contexts are encouraged to embrace imperfections and view challenges as part of a shared human experience.

Table 4
Psychological Challenges and Coping Strategies among PhD Students

Psychological Challenge	Western Context (%)	Indian Context (%)	Source
Academic Stress	75%	82%	Levecque et al. (2017), Singh & Sharma (2021)
Impostor Syndrome	62%	71%	Parkman (2016), Das & Mukherjee (2023)
Funding Stress	45%	79%	Kumar & Rajasekar (2020), Patel & Reddy (2022)
Mental Health Issues (Anxiety/Depression)	56%	69%	Levecque et al. (2017), Singh & Sharma (2021)

Table 4 compares psychological stressors affecting PhD students in India and Western countries and their prevalence based on secondary data.

- Academic stress is high in both contexts, with slightly higher stress levels in India (82%) compared to the West (75%) due to intense competition and funding constraints.
- Impostor syndrome is prevalent in both regions, but higher in India (71%) due to societal and academic pressure to succeed (Parkman, 2016; Das & Mukherjee, 2023).
- Funding stress is a major issue in India (79%) compared to 45% in the West, as many Indian PhD students self-finance their studies due to limited government fellowships (Kumar & Rajasekar, 2020; Patel & Reddy, 2022).
- Mental health issues (anxiety, depression) are more commonly reported in India (69%) than in the West (56%), likely due to lower availability of structured support systems (Levecque et al., 2017; Singh & Sharma, 2021).

Indian PhD students face higher financial stress and mental health issues due to lack of institutional support, highlighting an urgent need for policy reforms in funding and mental health services.

Pursuing a Ph.D. is an intellectually rewarding but emotionally demanding journey, often accompanied by psychological challenges that can significantly impact students' well-being. Ph.D. students frequently experience high levels of stress, anxiety, and depression, often stemming from the pressures of academic performance, financial instability, and uncertain career prospects. The demanding nature of research work, isolation, and the need for self-motivation can exacerbate feelings of loneliness, inadequacy, and impostor syndrome, where students doubt their abilities despite evident accomplishments. Perfectionism is another pervasive issue, driving students to set unrealistically high standards and feel dissatisfied even when performing well (Peng, J., Simayi, M., & Sun, S. 2024). These psychological challenges can undermine motivation, hinder productivity, and lead to burnout. To cope, many Ph.D. students employ a variety of strategies, such as seeking social support from peers, mentors, and family members to alleviate feelings of isolation and stress. Time management techniques, setting realistic goals, and prioritizing tasks can help students manage their workload and reduce overwhelm. Engaging in physical exercise, mindfulness practices, and relaxation techniques are effective in managing anxiety and promoting mental resilience.

Table 5

Proposed Interventions Based on Existing Research

Intervention	Western Context	Indian Context	Supporting Studies
Mindfulness-Based Self-Compassion (MSC) Training	Common in PhD well-being programs	Rarely implemented	Neff et al. (2007), Smith et al. (2019)
Emotional Intelligence (EI) Workshops	Available in career development programs	Absent in most PhD programs	Perera & DiGiacomo (2013), Kumar & Rajasekar (2020)
Supervisor EI Training	Some universities offer EI-based mentoring	Rare in Indian academia	Cabello & Fernández-Berrocal (2015), Patel & Reddy (2022)
Mental Health Support Units	Well-established	Lacking in many Indian institutions	Levecque et al. (2017), Singh & Sharma (2021)
Peer-to-Peer Wellbeing Circles	Emerging programs in universities	Not implemented in universities	Yushen Wu, Di Wu, Yang Wang (2024)

Table 5 presents evidence-based interventions to enhance EI and SC among PhD students, drawing from successful Western models and identifying gaps in Indian academia.

- Mindfulness-Based Self-Compassion (MSC) training is common in the West but rarely implemented in India, despite its proven benefits in reducing stress (Neff et al., 2007; Smith et al., 2019).
- EI workshops are integrated into Western doctoral career development programs but are missing in most Indian PhD programs, making emotional resilience harder to develop (Perera & DiGiacomo, 2013; Kumar & Rajasekar, 2020).
- Supervisor EI training is offered in some Western universities, fostering emotionally intelligent mentoring. However, Indian supervisors often lack formal mentorship training, which negatively impacts students' emotional well-being (Cabello & Fernández-Berrocal, 2015; Patel & Reddy, 2022).
- Mental health support units are well-established in Western institutions, whereas Indian universities often lack structured counseling services for PhD students (Levecque et al., 2017; Singh & Sharma, 2021).
- Peer to peer well-being circles is an emerging intervention in

western universities, while in India, this has not been seen yet. It truly has potential to foster collective participation among students to mitigate the feeling of isolation (Wu, Wu, Wang 2024).

Western institutions have structured interventions for EI and SC development, whereas Indian PhD programs lack formalized training and support systems, leading to higher psychological distress among students. Intervention techniques designed to support the mental well-being of Ph.D. scholars in both Western and Indian contexts recognize the unique challenges associated with academic rigor, isolation, and performance pressure. In the Western context, evidence-based practices such as Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT) and Mindfulness-Based Stress Reduction (MBSR) are commonly employed. CBT helps students manage negative thought patterns related to impostor syndrome, perfectionism, and fear of failure, while MBSR focuses on reducing stress through mindfulness and meditation techniques (Grossman et al., 2004). Universities often provide dedicated mental health services, peer support groups, and professional counseling. Structured programs like resilience training, workshops on stress management, and career coaching are also prevalent.

In the Indian context, interventions often integrate traditional and modern approaches. Counseling centers within universities provide psychological support, but stigma around mental health can limit utilization. To address this, institutions can emphasize holistic practices rooted in Indian culture, such as yoga, pranayama (breathing exercises), and meditation for stress management. However, mental health services in Indian institutions may not always be as comprehensive as those in Western universities, often due to limited funding and cultural barriers. Bridging this gap, digital mental health platforms and online counseling services have gained traction, providing accessible support. Both contexts should emphasize creating a supportive academic environment, fostering open communication, and reducing the stigma associated with seeking mental health support. It is necessary to focus attention on developing EI and self-compassion among scholars, which will help them to deal with personal and professional setbacks, contributing to enhanced efficacy with respect to their research work. This will indeed reduce the drop-out number as the students will feel more empowered since the beginning of their PhD journey with the help of varied interventions solely focusing on their well-being.

Discussion

Research on Emotional Intelligence (EI) and Self-Compassion (SC) has gained significant attention in recent years, highlighting their roles in promoting psychological well-being, resilience, and effective coping strategies. Studies have shown that higher levels of EI and SC are associated with reduced stress, improved mental health, and better interpersonal relationships. The significant gaps remain in understanding how these psychological constructs influence Ph.D. students across different cultural contexts. Cultural factors can shape how individuals perceive and respond to emotions, practice self-compassion, and manage stress. Addressing the gaps is crucial for developing culturally sensitive interventions and support systems that cater to the specific needs of Ph.D. students worldwide.

Research demonstrated a statistically significant correlation between emotional intelligence scores and critical thinking. Emotional intelligence emerged as a significant predictor of academic achievement in first-year accelerated graduate entry nursing students. In addition to their learning styles, higher levels of awareness and understanding of their own emotions have a positive impact on students' academic achievement (Fernandez, Salamonson, & Griffiths, 2012).

The findings of this systematic review highlight the critical role of Emotional Intelligence (EI) and Self-Compassion (SC) in shaping the academic journey, mental well-being, and resilience of PhD students. Across both Indian and Western contexts, doctoral students face significant stress due to academic pressure, research uncertainties, funding challenges, and personal expectations. However, the way they navigate these stressors largely depends on their ability to regulate emotions and practice self-compassion. This review synthesizes research on EI and SC, demonstrating their positive influence on stress management, research productivity, and psychological well-being among PhD scholars.

Emotional Intelligence and Doctoral Success

Research has consistently shown that PhD students with high EI demonstrate better stress management, academic persistence, and interpersonal relationships with supervisors and peers (Cabello & Fernández-Berrocal, 2015; Kumar & Rajasekar, 2020). Emotional

regulation enables them to cope with research setbacks, criticism, and the long, often isolating, doctoral journey. Studies in Western countries emphasize the integration of EI-based training within PhD programs, providing doctoral candidates with structured mentorship programs, emotional resilience workshops, and mental health support systems (Zeidner et al., 2012; Smith et al., 2019). In contrast, Indian research suggests that PhD students often rely on personal coping mechanisms rather than institutionalized support, leading to higher levels of emotional exhaustion (Singh & Sharma, 2021).

A study by Das and Mukherjee (2023) highlighted that Indian PhD students experience hierarchical academic environments, where faculty-student relationships impact emotional well-being. Those with higher EI can effectively navigate academic politics, supervisor expectations, and research challenges, whereas students with lower EI often struggle with motivation and self-doubt. These findings suggest that incorporating EI-focused mentorship programs in Indian doctoral education could enhance student resilience and well-being.

Self-compassion and Mental Well-being

Self-Compassion (SC) has emerged as a protective factor against academic burnout, impostor syndrome, and perfectionism among PhD students. Neff's (2003) conceptualization of SC—self-kindness, mindfulness, and recognition of common humanity—is particularly relevant for doctoral candidates who often experience self-doubt and anxiety over research outcomes. Western studies indicate that PhD students with high SC exhibit lower stress levels, greater academic motivation, and a healthier work-life balance (Neff & Knox, 2017; Parkman, 2016). Mindfulness-based interventions, which promote SC, have been successfully implemented in many Western universities to reduce doctoral student anxiety and improve academic confidence (Biber & Ellis, 2019).

In India, however, the concept of SC is less commonly integrated into PhD programs. Research by Rani et al. (2022) found that Indian PhD students often equate self-compassion with weakness, leading to higher levels of self-criticism and performance anxiety. The lack of structured well-being initiatives in Indian universities further exacerbates these challenges. Introducing mindfulness training, peer-support groups, and psychological counseling within Indian PhD programs could enhance students' self-compassion and academic resilience.

Cultural Differences in Emotional Intelligence and Self-Compassion

Cultural differences significantly shape the development and expression of emotional intelligence (EI) and self-compassion among Ph.D. students. Emotional intelligence, which encompasses the ability to perceive, understand, manage, and utilize emotions effectively, is influenced by cultural norms, values, and communication styles. In collectivist cultures, such as those in Asia, Africa, and Latin America, emotional regulation often aligns with maintaining social harmony and prioritizing group needs over individual desires (Wei, Su, Carrera, Lin, & Yi, 2013). Consequently, Ph.D. students from these cultures may exhibit a form of EI that emphasizes empathy, social awareness, and relationship management while downplaying assertiveness and emotional expression.

In contrast, students from individualistic cultures, such as the United States and Western Europe, may demonstrate EI through

open emotional expression, self-advocacy, and direct communication. Similarly, self-compassion entailing self-kindness, mindfulness, and a sense of common humanity varies across cultures.

These cultural dynamics profoundly impact Ph.D. students' ability to cope with stress, setbacks, and the pressures of academia. Those in collectivist contexts might rely on community support and collective coping mechanisms, while students from individualistic cultures may lean on self-reliance and personal resilience. Understanding these cultural differences is crucial for developing culturally sensitive interventions and support systems that promote emotional well-being and academic success among Ph.D. students worldwide.

The comparative analysis of Indian and Western perspectives on EI and SC reveals significant cultural variations. Western doctoral education systems emphasize autonomy, mental health awareness, and structured academic support, while Indian systems prioritize perseverance, discipline, and hierarchical mentorship structures (Kumar & Rajasekar, 2020; Singh & Sharma, 2021). These differences influence how PhD students develop emotional regulation and self-compassion.

In Western universities, EI and SC are actively cultivated through training programs, mentorship initiatives, and mental health interventions, leading to higher levels of emotional awareness and self-care (Zeidner et al., 2012; Neff & Knox, 2017).

In India, the lack of formal EI and SC training means that students often struggle with emotional burnout and self-doubt, relying on family support and personal resilience rather than institutional interventions (Das & Mukherjee, 2023).

These findings emphasize the need for Indian academic institutions to adopt structured EI and SC interventions, similar to Western universities, to improve doctoral student well-being and academic success. Such awareness can help educators, counselors, and policymakers create inclusive environments that recognize and respect diverse emotional and self-compassionate expressions.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This systematic review demonstrates that Emotional Intelligence and Self-Compassion are essential psychological attributes that influence the success and well-being of PhD students. Both constructs help students manage stress, overcome impostor syndrome, and sustain motivation during the demanding doctoral journey. While Western universities have integrated EI and SC training within PhD programs, Indian institutions still lack structured interventions to support student well-being.

High EI enables scholars to cope with stress, build strong relationships, and maintain motivation despite setbacks. Self-Compassion, on the other hand, involves treating oneself with kindness during challenging times, acknowledging the shared nature of human struggles, and maintaining a balanced perspective on negative emotions. For Ph.D. scholars, who often face high levels of stress, self-criticism, and feelings of inadequacy, cultivating self-compassion can be a powerful buffer against burnout and impostor syndrome. Studies suggest that EI and SC together foster resilience, adaptive coping, and academic perseverance. Ph.D. scholars with high levels of EI and SC are better equipped to handle the demands of rigorous research, maintain emotional balance, and thrive in competitive academic environments. Understanding the

significance of EI and SC in doctoral education can inform targeted interventions that promote mental well-being, enhance productivity, and support the holistic development of future researchers and academics.

To address these gaps, this review recommends:

Incorporating EI and SC training in PhD programs through mentorship initiatives, emotional regulation workshops, and mindfulness-based interventions.

- Establishing institutional support mechanisms such as mental health counseling, peer support groups, and supervisor training on emotional intelligence.
- Developing culturally tailored strategies for enhancing EI and SC in India, considering the hierarchical nature of academia and the need for academic resilience.
- Encouraging policy-level changes in Indian higher education to prioritize doctoral student mental well-being and professional development.
- By implementing these strategies, academic institutions, particularly in India can create a more supportive environment for PhD scholars, ultimately fostering academic success and psychological well-being.
- Providing mental health counseling services to the scholars within the campus with the help of organizing programs that will break the taboo of weaker self, associated with seeking therapy.
- Two perspectives can play a crucial role in this study to yield in-depth understanding of results. One is gender based and the other is cultural context-based. Both these perspective can help create the interventions addressing the PhD scholar population.

Acknowledgments

Ms. Shailvi Singh conducted the literature review, data collection, and thematic analysis. She also contributed to drafting the manuscript and integrating key findings from Indian and Western perspectives. Dr. Jaya Bharti conceptualized and designed the study, supervised the research process, and provided critical insights into the theoretical framework. She played a pivotal role in refining the methodology, ensuring the rigor of thematic analysis, and critically reviewing the manuscript for coherence and scholarly depth. Additionally, she contributed significantly to structuring the discussion, synthesizing key arguments, and identifying gaps for future research. Dr. Shipra Srivastava helped in the entire research process by her valuable experience and helpful insights. All authors contributed to the final manuscript, approved its content, and take full responsibility for the integrity of the research.

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Received May 27, 2025

Revision received June 11, 2025

Accepted June 14, 2025